

ADDRESSING CYBERSECURITY IN ENERGY ISLAND

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The E-LAND (elandh2020) project aims to enable businesses to become Local Energy Systems (LES). Mainland regions such as isolated villages, small cities, urban districts or rural areas often have issues with weak or non-existing grid connections. These areas are known as energy islands. The continued decarbonization of the energy sector using renewable energy sources provides both interesting opportunities for LES while simultaneously challenging existing electricity networks. The E-LAND project aims to enable both optimization and control of multi-vector local energy system by providing a modular set of methodologies, supported by ICT tools for both digital systems and for business aspects. In this paper we present the projects' safety activities, with the focus on identifying threats and potential risks as part of the system landscape between operational systems (OT) and enterprise IT systems.

A typical LES consist of an integrated energy system consisting of Distributed Energy Resources (DER) that is used for load control, energy storage and consumption optimization. All of this is achieved by a software toolbox that integrates the distributed RES, and storage assets at the edges of the electricity grid, and optimally balancing these assets with other energy-vectors, while extending the lifetime of current infrastructures. The toolbox introduces the possibility to send control set point back to the LES for semi automatically energy optimization of the island.

Addressing cybersecurity threats in energy island is about balancing the technical infrastructure and assets risks with business needs and protecting data from unintentional information disclosure and data leakage (ENISA, 2013). Every organization that implementing smart grid functionality address cybersecurity issues that are diverse and complex for the organization. Especially when relying on existing legacy systems and infrastructure when interoperate with new assets connected to the smart grid. This potentially introduce new operational risk for the operator.

The paper summarizes identified cybersecurity risks relevant for energy island as identified during the development phase of the E-LAND toolbox. Some of these risks include the LES operator's exposure of existing legacy operational (OT) infrastructure, security and privacy concerns in multi-cloud environments, asset hardening and integration requirements, establishing a common baseline for network security and best practices, and data ownership and management to name some. The risks are discussed in more detail and exemplified through general use case examples before suggested mitigations for the risks are provided.

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Keywords: E-LAND, energy island, cybersecurity, risks, privacy, data protection, system integrity.

References:

Eland website: <https://elandh2020.eu/>

ENSIA (2013), Smart Grid Threat Landscape and good practice (SGAM)